

A NUMERICAL STUDY ON NON-SYNCHRONOUS VIBRATION OF A UHBR FAN THROUGH
NONLINEAR FLUID-STRUCTURE INTERACTION

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ABSTRACT

To understand the critical issue of Non-Synchronous Vibration (NSV) in Ultra-High Bypass Ratio (UHBR) fans, which restricts the development of advanced aero-engines, this study focuses on the ECL5 UHBR fan and conducts numerical research using a nonlinear Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) method. During this study, the differences between CFD predictions and experimental aerodynamic characteristics were examined. The mechanism of circumferential propagation of aerodynamic disturbances was clarified, and the occurrence of NSV was successfully predicted using the nonlinear FSI method. The predicted aerodynamic wavenumbers and characteristic frequencies showed good agreement with the experimental results. This work provides a reliable approach for predicting NSV and contributes to a deeper understanding of the underlying mechanisms of the phenomenon.

Keywords: Non-Synchronous Vibration; Fluid-Structure Interaction; Ultra-High Bypass Ratio fan

NOMENCLATURE

BTW	Backward Traveling Wave
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
EO	Engine Order
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transform
DP	Design Point
FSI	Fluid-Structure Interaction
F_a	Aerodynamic force

FEM	Finite Element Method
FTW	Forward Traveling Wave
HCF	High-Cycle Fatigue
LCO	limit cycle of oscillations
M	Mass matrix
\dot{m}_{std}	Standard mass-flow rate (kg/s)
N_a	Aerodynamic wave number
N_v	Vibration wave number
N	Total blade number
NB	Blade number
ND	Nodal Diameter
NC	Near Choke
NS	Near Stall
OP	Operating Point
Ω	Angular velocity (rad/s)
$\Pi_{t,stage}$	Stage total pressure ratio
PP	Peak Pressure ratio
SE	Stage Exit
SG	Strain Gauge
URANS	Unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations
x	Blade displacement vector
\dot{x}	Blade velocity vector
\ddot{x}	Blade acceleration vector
Φ	Mode shape component

1. INTRODUCTION

Blade vibration is a primary cause of High-Cycle Fatigue (HCF), which can lead to the blade failure, posing a significant threat to engine structural integrity and flight safety [1]. Traditional vibration analysis has focused on Synchronous Vibration. This type of vibration is excited by circumferential non-uniformities in the flow field, such as upstream struts [2] or inlet distortions [3]. Its frequency is an integer multiple of the engine's rotational speed (engine order), making it predictable through a Campbell Diagram and manageable during the design phase via frequency tuning.

However, with the continuous advancement of engine performance, a more complex and perilous phenomenon so called Non-Synchronous Vibration (NSV) has become increasingly prominent, emerging as a critical challenge that constrains the development of advanced aero-engines. This phenomenon was first reported by Baumgartner et al. [4] in 1995. During tests on a 10-stage high-pressure gas turbine developed by Rolls-Royce, non-engine order high-amplitude vibrations of the first-stage compressor rotor blades were detected using pressure pulse sensors mounted on the casing inner wall and strain gauges attached to the blade surfaces. The underlying cause was identified as rotating instability. Kielb et al. [5] were the first to systematically describe the causes and triggering conditions of NSV, and demonstrated that its occurrence is accompanied by frequency and phase locking.

The fundamental mechanism responsible for NSV remains unclear. The three primary coupling mechanisms that have been proposed are rotating instability induced vibration [6], the jet-core feedback mechanism [7], and acoustic resonance [8]. Rotating instability induced NSVs have been observed in both experimental studies and numerical simulations. Möller et al. [9-11] performed extensive investigations on the TUD transonic compressor rig, showing that NSVs are induced by the tip unsteady flow. In the relative coordinate system, the motion direction is opposite to the rotational speed, resulting in a forward-traveling structural wave. A larger tip clearance increases the blocked flow region, thereby enhancing the likelihood of blade vibration. Zha et al. [13,14] employed high-fidelity CFD to investigate the aerodynamic origins of NSV and the effect of tip clearance size on the excitation frequency. They showed that the tip flow instability is the main cause of the NSV and the convex-type shape tip clearance substantially change the instability frequency.

A stall-driven type NSV [15-17] was observed in a multi-stage high speed compressor operating at part speed, which was caused by stage mismatching. A newly identified form of NSV [18] can occur at high crosswind conditions when the flow at the intake lip separates and the disturbances caused by flow separation become unsteady.

Some theoretical simplified models have been developed for the prediction of NSV. Hollenbach et al. [19,20] employed a reduced-order model based on the Van der Pol oscillator to investigate the mechanisms underlying NSV in turbomachinery. Stapelfeldt et al. [21] developed a semi-analytical model calibrated with numerical results. The model can simulate the

lock-in process and accurately predicting unstable vibration modes. A series of studies [22-24] conducted by the Ecole Centrale de Lyon have shown that for UHBR fans, it is challenging to reproduce the NSV of partial rotational speeds through numerical simulation.

The aim of this study is threefold: first, to validate CFD predictions by comparing the computed aerodynamic characteristics with experimental measurements; second, to employ a full-annulus URANS approach to analyze the propagation mechanisms of unsteady disturbances and identify the dominant frequencies associated with each aerodynamic wavenumber; and third, to apply a nonlinear fluid-structure interaction method to predict the onset of NSV. The findings demonstrate that this approach can reliably reproduce the experimentally observed aerodynamic and structural wavenumbers, confirming its predictive accuracy.

2. NONLINEAR FLUID-SOLID INTERACTION METHODS

The linear aeroelastic analysis method based on a prescribed vibration is widely applied in NSV research. This offers a convenient approach for determining the lock-in range if unsteady frequency exist, but fail to directly predict the onset of NSV and determine the unstable nodal diameter. To address this limitation, this paper proposes a nonlinear FSI method, and attempts to use this method to gain deeper insights into NSV.

The core of the nonlinear FSI method lies in solving the dynamic equations to capture blade vibrations, thereby providing a more realistic feedback effect on the flow field. The aeroelastic response and stability problems of turbomachinery can be solved by dynamic equations:

$$M\ddot{x}(t) + C\dot{x}(t) + Kx(t) = F_a(x, \dot{x}, t) \quad (1)$$

where M is mass, C is damping, K is stiffness, and $F_a(x, \dot{x}, t)$ is the aerodynamic loading which is provided by CFD. The nonlinear fluid-structure coupling method employed in this paper simultaneously solves the fluid domain and the structural domain.

FIGURE 1 presents the numerical procedure of the adopted FSI coupling approach. The computation is performed in a partitioned manner, with the fluid and structural domains solved separately while exchanging data at each time step. On the fluid side, a CFD solution is first obtained at time step n . The corresponding structural displacements are then mapped back to the physical space to deform the computational mesh by solving the displacement diffusion equation, after which the CFD solution is advanced to the next time step.

On the structural side, the modal forces f_n of time n extracted from the CFD are applied to the structural dynamic equation.

$$f_n = \phi^T \Delta F_a \quad (2)$$

where ϕ is mode shape vector, ΔF is the local unsteady pressure. The structural dynamic equation is integrated using the

FIGURE 1 ILLUSTRATION OF THE NONLINEAR FLUID-STRUCTURE COUPLING APPROACH

Newmark- β method to obtain the modal displacements at step $n + 1$. The implicit Newmark scheme, with $\beta = 1/4$ and $\gamma = 1/2$, ensures the unconditional stability of the structural time integration. Finally, the updated displacements are transferred back to the fluid solver, completing one coupling cycle. This procedure establishes a consistent two-way coupling between the fluid and structural solvers.

In the following, additional details of the structural solution are presented. Typically, the vibration of a blade row can be expressed as the superposition of a forward and a backward traveling wave. The travelling wave formulation can be written as:

$$x_m(t, \theta) = A_{m,FTW} \cos(m\theta - \omega t) + A_{m,BTW} \cos(m\theta + \omega t) \quad (3)$$

The mode shape of travelling wave is time-dependent, so it is inconvenient to impose this as a boundary function in the CFD solver. To address this issue, a standing wave model is employed. The standing wave formulation can be written as:

$$x_m(t, \theta) = A_{m,cos} \cos(\omega t) \cos(m\theta) + A_{m,sin} \cos(\omega t) \sin(m\theta) \quad (4)$$

The original travelling wave mode shape and converted standing wave mode shape can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{m,FTW}(x_0, t) &= \cos(m\theta - \omega t) \\ \Phi_{m,BTW}(x_0, t) &= \cos(m\theta + \omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{m,cos}(x_0) &= \cos(m\theta) \\ \Phi_{m,sin}(x_0) &= \sin(m\theta) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The mode shape of standing wave is time-independent. Since the modes of each ND are mutually orthogonal, the blade motion in each mode can be represented as the superposition of all standing wave modes. This modeling method offers the advantage of calculating the motion of all NDs in a single simulation, which markedly improves computational efficiency.

3. NUMERICAL METHODS

3.1 Test case: ECL5

This study focuses on the ECL5, an ultra-high bypass ratio (UHBR) fan stage. Housed at the Laboratoire de Mécanique des Fluides et d'Acoustique (LMFA) of École Centrale de Lyon, the ECL5 facility is a state-of-the-art test rig specifically designed to investigate the complex aerodynamic, structural dynamic, and acoustic phenomena of next-generation civil aero-engines [12]. A low-transonic, 16-bladed carbon fiber design was developed by LMFA with a predicted pressure ratio of 1.35, high isentropic efficiency of 92.6% at design conditions [25]. Key parameters of the design are summarized in TABLE 1.

TABLE 1 KEY PARAMETERS OF ECL5 UHBR FAN

Design parameters	Values
Number of fan blades (-)	16
Fan diameter (mm)	508
Design pressure ratio (-)	1.35
Design relative Mach number tip (-)	0.99 (95% Span)
Design rotating speed (RPM)	11,000
Design mass flow (kg/s)	36
pressure coefficient (-)	0.65
flow coefficient (-)	0.61
Hub to shroud ratio (-)	0.29

FIGURE 2 presents a schematic view of the ECL5 geometry together with probe positions, the blade and intake geometry. In the intake labeled in, total pressure and temperature rakes are integrated for performance measurements. There also two traversable rakes downstream of the stage (stage exit (SE)). The mass flow rate \dot{m}_{std} are corrected to international standard atmosphere (ISA) conditions.

FIGURE 2 SCHEMATIC VIEW OF MACHINE CORE AND PROBE POSITIONS [26]

3.2 CFD set-up

The commercial 3D compressible Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes flow solver Ansys CFX is chosen to perform the CFD analysis, with implicit time-marching. The numerical scheme used is second-order upwind. The $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model [27] is applied for all CFD simulations. The domains used

for this study together with boundary conditions used is shown in FIGURE 3, the intake duct is simplified to a straight duct. Uniform total pressure and temperature boundary conditions, and zero flow angles are prescribed at the inlet. At exit a choked nozzle is used to control the flow.

The grids of the fan and the OGV, respectively, contain 1.06 million and 0.27 million nodes per passage, and the y^+ of the first layer from the surface is about 1. This grid was obtained after a grid convergence study. (see Appendix 1).

The blade is modeled using the hot shape fan that varies with rotational speed. The study is conducted at 100% and 80% rotational speeds, with uniform tip clearances of 0.9 mm and 1.0 mm, respectively.

The single-passage mesh was replicated to form a full-annulus model, yielding a total of 25 million grid nodes. A temporal resolution of 800 timesteps per shaft revolution was employed. The circumferential development of disturbances was examined using 360 uniformly distributed numerical probes positioned at the fan blade tip leading edge, where transient pressure fluctuations will be recorded in URANS simulation. The computational domain and probe locations are shown in FIGURE 4.

- Total pressure and temperature (ISA Sea Level Conditions)
- Zero flow angles

FIGURE 3 COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

FIGURE 4 COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN AND PROBE LOCATIONS

3.3 Comparison between Numerical and experimental data

FIGURE 5 compares the steady performance of the fan stage, between the CFD results and the experimental data. The results demonstrate that CFD method used in this paper is accurate in predicting the performance as well as stability limits. At 80% rotational speed close to the choke point, there is an

underestimation of isentropic efficiency was also observed in [25].

FIGURE 6 presents the total pressure contour at the stator exit (SE), compares the contours of total pressure between CFD and test data for two operating points marked in FIGURE 5 at 100% and 80% speed. The plot shows that at DP operating point there is a good agreement between CFD and measured data, both showing the same location and strength in blockage.

For the PP operating point both CFD and measured data show a decrease the tip blockage as compared to DP operating point. However, the tip blockage is stronger in CFD than measured data, especially at 100% speed.

FIGURE 7 presents the radial profile of the stage total pressure ratio. Different operating conditions: near choke (NC), design point (DP), peak pressure ratio (PP), and near stall (NS). The CFD simulation overestimated the separation losses in the OGV region; however, this effect became less pronounced in the radial distribution after circumferential averaging. Furthermore, under high-load conditions, the increased unsteadiness of the fan blade tips leads to deviations in the predicted tip flow field for both PP and NS operating points.

Another reason for this deviation is that under high-load conditions, separation on the suction surface initiates in the blade mid-span, and the CFD-predicted separation point differs from the experimental observation.

FIGURE 5 FAN STAGE CHARACTERISTIC OF CFD AND EXP DATA

FIGURE 6 TOTAL PRESSURE CONTOUR AT SE NORMALIZED WITH MASS-AVERAGED STAGE TOTAL PRESSURE RATIO

FIGURE 7 RADIAL PROFILE OF STAGE TOTAL PRESSURE RATIO

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Unsteady without blade vibration

Initially, unsteady computations were conducted in the absence of blade vibration to capture the spontaneous formation and progression of disturbances at high operating points.

FIGURE 8 shows the steady and unsteady characteristics of the fan stage. Three URANS operating points, denoted as OP1, OP2, and OP3, are investigated in this study. It can be observed that the total pressure ratio $\Pi_{t,stage}$ predicted by URANS is

higher than that obtained with RANS and is closer to the experimental measurements.

FIGURE 8 STEADY AND UNSTEADY FAN STAGE CHARACTERISTICS

The NSV occurrence range in experiment, obtained from strain gauge (SG) and wall pressure transducers (WPT) measurements reported by Schneider [28], is illustrated in FIGURE 9. It is observed that the \dot{m}_{std} at OP2 and OP3 lie within the broadband disturbance region of aerodynamic waves and the \dot{m}_{std} at OP1 is out of the range. If the FSI simulations presented in this study fully align with the experiments, OP2 and OP3 will exhibit disturbances with frequencies approaching the natural frequency of mode 3, whereas OP3 will also display disturbances near the natural frequency of mode 2.

FIGURE 9 THE STRAIN GAUGE (SG) AND WALL PRESSURE TRANSDUCERS (WPT) SPECTROGRAM [28]

In FIGURE 10, the CFD and measured tip low field at operating condition OP2 is compared. It can be observed that the CFD and EXP results show good agreement in terms of time-averaged static casing pressure. The deviation of pressure, normalized by its maximum value, is used to quantify the pressure fluctuations. In the CFD results, the region of

intensified pressure fluctuation is concentrated closer to the leading edge, whereas the suction surface exhibits weaker fluctuations than measured data. Since the calculation of modal forces is based on pressure fluctuations, the values near the mid-span may deviate from the experimental results. However, because the deformations of modes 2 and 3 are relatively small in this region, the resulting deviation is expected to be limited.

The circumferential propagation of aerodynamic disturbances in the tip region is visualized using radial vorticity. FIGURE 11 compares the radial vorticity at 98% blade height under three different operating conditions. Pullan et al. [29] demonstrated that spike-type stall inception in compressors is associated with leading-edge spillage and may occur even in the absence of tip clearance. A comparable phenomenon was identified in this fan stage, but it did not progress to stall at this speed. In OP1, aerodynamic disturbances are induced by the periodic circumferential propagation of leading-edge radial separation, without spillage. By contrast, OP2 and OP3 feature both leading-edge spillage and non-uniform propagation of disturbances, giving rise to multiple aerodynamic wavenumbers circumferentially. The schematic of aerodynamic disturbance propagation is shown in FIGURE 12. These two flow mechanisms exert different effects on the propagation of aerodynamic disturbances, as illustrated in FIGURE 13.

FIGURE 10 COMPARISON OF TIME-AVERAGED STATIC PRESSURE AND STANDARD DEVIATION ON THE CASING BETWEEN EXP AND CFD

FIGURE 11 RADIAL VORTICITY DISTRIBUTION AT 98% SPAN

FIGURE 12 SCHEMATIC OF AERODYNAMIC DISTURBANCE PROPAGATION: (A) WITHOUT LEADING-EDGE SPILLAGE; (B) WITH LEADING-EDGE SPILLAGE

The evolution of the circumferential profile and modal content is presented in FIGURE 13. A one-dimensional Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) is applied to the pressure data obtained from probes uniformly distributed around the circumference. Assuming N probes evenly spaced around the circumference, measuring pressure values $p_0, p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{N-1}$, the complex amplitude of the k^{th} circumferential mode is calculated as:

$$A_k(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} p_n(t) \cdot e^{-i \frac{(2\pi kn)}{N}} \quad (7)$$

where $p_n(t)$ is the pressure value from the n^{th} probe at time t . $A_k(t)$ is the complex amplitude of the k^{th} mode at time t . The pressure presented here is expressed in the rotating frame of reference.

The circumferential evolution is shown in FIGURE 13. The flow field is first obtained under the stable OP1 operating

condition. Subsequently, the flow is reduced to the OP3 condition by gradually closing the nozzle. The OP1 flow field already exhibits clear periodicity by the third revolution, and because of the circumferential aerodynamic mode number N_a matches the blade number $N = 16$, significant axial oscillations are present. This phenomenon can be explained by FIGURE 12. In the absence of leading-edge spillage, the unsteady behavior in adjacent passages remains isolated. Consequently, the wave phases across all blade passages remain consistent.

FIGURE 13 EVOLUTION OF CIRCUMFERENTIAL PROFILE AND MODAL CONTENT IN ROTATING FRAME

However, this phenomenon can only occur under ideal conditions, as the CFD results showed a single aerodynamic wavenumber, whereas experiments revealed multiple

wavenumbers generated almost simultaneously during throttling (see FIGURE 8). This phenomenon may be attributed to geometric deviations (e.g., stagger and tip clearance), which alter the propagation speed of aerodynamic disturbances. This phenomenon was previously investigated in detail by Tharreau et al. [24] through nonuniform tip clearance modeling, but this aspect is beyond the scope of the present discussion.

Upon further throttling, the onset of leading-edge spillage flow initiated cross-passage propagation of aerodynamic disturbances, thereby inducing interference between the unsteady responses of adjacent passages. This interference exhibits strong nonlinearity, and even after 20 shaft revolutions of computation, no stable dominant N_a is observed. This phenomenon was also observed in a high-speed compressor [15]. The aerodynamic waves with wavenumbers 13 and 14 predicted by CFD were also observed in the experiments (at operating point OP3), whereas the lower-order waves ($2 \sim 4$) were not detected.

FIGURE 14 shows the circumferential mode characteristics in the absolute frame. Data sampling was performed over the final five revolutions of the OP3 operating condition. It can be observed that within the range of $0.4 \sim 0.6$ BPF, two groups of aerodynamic waves appear, with wave number and frequency exhibiting a positive correlation. The characteristic frequency $\frac{\omega_{\text{aero}}}{\Omega_r}$ is indicated after the aerodynamic wavenumber. The dominant aerodynamic wavenumbers and their corresponding frequencies measured in the experiment are listed in TABLE 2. It can be observed that the frequencies of aerodynamic waves with potential coupling to the mode 3 structural vibration exhibit good agreement with the experimental results. The aerodynamic wave numbers associated with modes 2 and 1 are not observed at this operating point. From the aerodynamic perspective alone, it is difficult to predict the occurrence of NSV or the number of resulting vibration waves.

FIGURE 14 CIRCUMFERENTIAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE ABSOLUTE FRAME

4.2 Unsteady with blade vibration

In the next step, the nonlinear fluid–structure interaction method will be applied to the full-annulus simulation. The specific setup procedures will first be introduced.

The first three fan mode shapes obtained from FEM are presented in FIGURE 15. The mode shapes in this study are consistent with those reported in [12]. Mode 1 is predominantly

a pure bending mode. Mode 2 and Mode 3 exhibit significant torsional components at the blade tip, with their nodal lines intersecting the trailing edge and leading edge. The single-blade mode shape is circumferentially expanded to form the assembly mode shape of each standing wave. The modal masses of each order are calculated based on the aerodynamic damping described in [12].

TABLE 2 NONSYNCHRONOUS VIBRATION MODES EXPERIMENTALLY OBSERVED AT 80% SPEED [26]

	$\frac{\omega_v^R}{\Omega_r}$	N_v	$\frac{\omega_v^R}{\Omega_r}$	N_a	$\frac{\omega_v^S}{\Omega_r}$	$\frac{\omega_v^R}{\Omega_r}$	$\frac{\Omega_a^S}{\Omega_r}$
	(EO)		(EO)		(EO)	(EO)	
Mode3	5.87	2	7.87	-15	8.44	6.56	0.56
				-14	8.13	5.87	0.58
				-13	7.33	5.67	0.56
				-12	6.77	5.23	0.56
				-11	6.19	4.81	0.56
Mode2	4.52	6	10.52	-10	5.47	4.53	0.55
				-8	4.55	3.45	0.57
				-7	3.98	3.02	0.58
Mode1	1.87	-5	12.87	5	3.11	1.89	0.63
				4	2.23	1.77	0.56

Note: Phase locked pressure waves are in bold text.

FIGURE 15 NORMALIZED MODE SHAPES FROM FEM

The nonlinear FSI implementation in CFX is carried out using USER Fortran. Data transfer takes place at the end of each physical time step: once a CFD solution step is completed, the modal forces are passed to the user defined Fortran code to calculate the modal displacements. These displacements are then transmitted back to the solver before the next CFD step begins. Through mesh deformation, they are converted into physical displacements, after which the next solution step proceeds.

The unsteady simulation with blade vibration was initialized using the URANS solution without blade vibration. Three coupling cases were selected: Mode 3 under OP2 and OP3 conditions, and Mode 2 under the OP3 condition. It should be noted that the blade modal vibration patterns obtained from FEM

All NDs share the same vibration frequency, and both modal displacements and modal forces f_n are obtained within a single calculation. However, due to the significant differences in frequency and mode shape between Mode3 ND1 and other NDs,

only its modal forces are considered, while its modal displacements are excluded, to prevent unintended impacts on the aerodynamic characteristics. The modal mass of Mode 2 was doubled to prevent convergence issues caused by mesh deformation. The modal frequencies are 4.52 EO for Mode 2 and 5.93 EO for Mode 3.

As the calculation directly yields the standing waves, a conversion into the corresponding traveling wave is performed using equations 5 and 6. The converted results are presented in FIGURE 16. The results of all three cases predicted the occurrence of NSV. For both OP2 and OP3, the dominant Mode 3 structural vibration waves correspond to the ND2 FTW which is excited by $N_a=14$. The agreement between the predicted dominant structural wavenumber and the experimental result indicates that the calculation results are reliable. At OP3, a beating vibration of ND2 FTW with a frequency of about 50 Hz occurred. This suggests that the unsteady frequency predicted by CFD is lower than that observed in the experimental measurements. It is worth noting that, since unsteady flow exhibits broadband characteristics, when the blade's natural frequency falls within this range, NSV cannot be effectively avoided by frequency-shifting. Such an approach merely alters the dominant aerodynamic wavenumber that triggers the vibration, rather than eliminating the phenomenon.

FIGURE 17 further illustrates the frequency spectra of the modal forces for different nodal diameters. The vibration frequencies corresponding to Mode 2 and Mode 3 are denoted by the purple and pink planes, respectively. The white dotted lines indicate the intersections of the modal force with the vibration frequencies. It can be observed that, under the OP3 condition, the modal force spectrum peak corresponding to Mode 2 ND4 intersects with 4.52 EO, whereas under the OP2 condition, the modal force spectrum peak corresponding to Mode 3 ND2 intersects with 5.93 EO. This phenomenon accounts for the limit cycle oscillations (LCO) observed in Mode 2 ND4 FTW and Mode 3 ND2 FTW. It can also be observed that the frequency peak of the modal force decreases with increasing nodal diameter across all operating conditions. This phenomenon is consistent with the previous findings regarding the variation of the frequency of absolute aerodynamic waves with wave number.

Regarding the intersection of Mode 3 ND1 with 5.93 EO, only the modal forces were computed in this case. To prevent aerodynamic wave lock-in ND1 and to avoid coupling effects between ND2 and the aerodynamics, the modal displacement of ND1 was constrained. Nevertheless, it can be inferred that if the actual frequency and mode shape of ND1 are similar to those of the other NDs, ND1 would become the dominant structural vibration wave.

It was shown that the nonlinear FSI approach can predict the NSV phenomenon at 80% rotational speed. Since two distinct sets of circumferential disturbances ($N_a = 13, 14, 15$) and ($N_a = 3, 4, 5$) with different orders and characteristic frequencies were observed in both the rotating and stationary coordinate systems, it is inaccurate to predict in advance which modes will be excited before applying the nonlinear FSI. In this study, the challenge of

predictive modeling arises from the fact that NSV is simultaneously governed by the frequency difference between modal force and blade natural frequency, as well as by aliasing phenomena.

FIGURE 16 TRAVELING WAVE MODAL DISPLACEMENT OF DIFFERENT OPERATING POINT AND IMPOSED MODE SHAPE

As shown in FIGURE 9, in the range when NSV occurs, Mode 3 is affected by the FTW with a wave number of 14, and Mode 2 is affected by the FTW with a wave number of 12. It can be established that two conditions must be satisfied for aliasing to occur. Firstly, the characteristic frequency of the N_a must be close to the N_v frequency. Secondly, the sum of the N_a and the N_v must equal the total number of blades.

The contour of axial velocity contour at fan exit is shown in FIGURE 18. It can be observed that as \dot{m}_{std} decreases, the number of stall cells gradually decreases. For OP2 Mode3, the stall cell number is 15, the frequency difference between modal force and blade natural frequency is smallest when $N_a = 14$; for OP3 Mode3, the stall cell number is 14, the frequency difference between modal force and blade natural frequency is smallest

when $N_a = 15$. Since no lock-in phenomenon has been observed in Mode3, the blade vibration is dominated by the aerodynamic wave whose characteristic frequency is closest to the blade's natural frequency. Similar to the phenomenon reported by Brandstetter et al.[30], the tip deformation associated with Mode 2 is a critical factor that can markedly modify the flow field and change the stall cell number, which makes the stall cells uneven. However, for Mode 3, the vibration amplitude at the leading-edge of blade tip is nearly zero, substantially reducing its influence on the aerodynamic waves. This may explain why OP3 ND2 FTW did not experience lock-in.

FIGURE 17 FREQUENCY SPECTRUM OF MODAL FORCES

FIGURE 18 CONTOUR OF AXIAL VELOCITY CONTOUR AT FAN EXIT

5. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the mechanism and prediction of Non-Synchronous Vibration (NSV) in the ECL5 UHBR fan at 80% rotational speed. First, the aerodynamic characteristics predicted by CFD were compared with experimental data, showing good agreement in terms of total pressure ratio, isentropic efficiency, and flow-field pressure distribution. A full-annulus URANS approach was then employed to analyze the circumferential propagation of unsteady disturbances, allowing the dominant aerodynamic wavenumbers and their characteristic frequencies to be identified. Finally, a nonlinear FSI method was employed to accurately predict the structural vibration waves during NSV.

By analyzing three representative operating conditions, it was found that the unsteady flow in the fan exhibited circumferential propagation of aerodynamic disturbances in the tip region of the fan blade. A criterion for determining whether the aerodynamic wavenumber exhibits broadband characteristics is the occurrence of leading-edge spillage.

Through nonlinear FSI, it was predicted that both Mode 2 and Mode 3 would experience NSV, with the corresponding structural vibration waves being ND4 FTW and ND2 FTW, respectively. These results are in close agreement with the experimentally observed Mode 2 ND6 FTW and Mode 3 ND2 FTW. Aliasing between aerodynamic waves and structural waves is considered an important influencing factor.

This work presents a reliable approach for predicting NSV and offers valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms of the phenomenon.

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APPENDIX1: Grid convergence study

To verify grid convergence, three sets of grids of per passage (coarse: FAN 0.41 million cells and OGV 0.09 million cells, medium: FAN 1.05 million cells and OGV 0.27 million cells, and fine: FAN 2.52 million cells and OGV 0.60 million cells) are compared. As shown in FIGURE A1, the performance map demonstrates that the predicted deviations in total pressure ratio, adiabatic efficiency, and mass flow rate between the medium and fine grids are negligible. The details of grids in shown in TABLE A2.

FIGURE A1 EFFECT OF GRID DENSITY ON PREDICTING THE ECL5 PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS

TABLE A1 DETAILS OF ECL5 GRIDS

Grid topology		Coarse	Medium	Fine
FAN	Total radial grid point	65	85	125
	Tip gap radial grid point	9	17	25
	Total tangential grid point	33	57	81
	Total axial grid point	77	117	153
	Tip gap O-grid point	9	13	21
	Total grid point (million)	0.41	1.05	2.52
Grid topology		Coarse	Medium	Fine
OGV	Total radial grid point	37	53	73
	Total tangential grid point	17	25	41
	Total axial grid point	57	73	101
	Total grid point (million)	0.09	0.27	0.60

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